

A Cross-Sectional Study on Internet Addiction among Medical Students in Udaipur, RajasthanShikha Mehta¹, Sharad Mehta², Shivani Vihan³, Jatin Prajapati⁴, Ravindra Pal⁵, Anand Singh⁶¹Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, RNT Medical College, Udaipur, Rajasthan, India²Professor, Department of Dermatology, RNT Medical College, Udaipur, Rajasthan, India^{3,4,5,6} PG student, Department of Community Medicine, RNT Medical College, Udaipur, Rajasthan, India

Received: 01-03-2025 / Revised: 15-04-2025 / Accepted: 21-05-2025

Corresponding author: Dr. Jatin Prajapati

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract**Background:** The internet has become an indispensable tool for education, communication, and entertainment. However, excessive use may lead to internet addiction, particularly among youth and students in demanding academic environments like medical colleges. This study aimed to assess the prevalence and pattern of internet addiction among medical students in Udaipur, Rajasthan.**Objectives:** To determine the prevalence of internet addiction among medical students using Young's Internet Addiction Test (IAT), and to assess its association with sociodemographic and behavioural factors.**Methods:** A cross-sectional study was conducted among 392 undergraduate medical students from a government medical college in Udaipur. Participants were selected using stratified random sampling. Data were collected using a semi-structured questionnaire and Young's Internet Addiction Test (IAT). Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 25. Chi-square tests were used to determine associations between addiction levels and selected variables. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.**Results:** Out of 392 participants, 23.5% had normal internet use, 44.1% had mild addiction, 28.3% had moderate addiction, and 4.1% were found to have severe addiction. Male students, hostel residents, and those using the internet for more than 4 hours daily were significantly more likely to show moderate to severe levels of addiction ($p < 0.05$). Non-academic usage was also associated with higher IAT scores. No significant association was found between year of study and internet addiction levels.**Conclusion:** Internet addiction is highly prevalent among medical students, with nearly one-third showing moderate to severe addiction. Risk factors include male gender, excessive usage time, and hostel residence. Institutions should implement targeted awareness, digital hygiene programs, and provide psychological support to prevent the adverse effects of excessive internet use.**Keywords:** Internet Addiction, Medical Students, Young's IAT, Udaipur, Digital Behavior, Risk Factors, Hostel, Screen Time.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

The advent of the internet has dramatically transformed the way people communicate, learn, and interact. With its widespread accessibility and convenience, the internet has become an indispensable part of daily life, especially among students and professionals alike.

Among the various user groups, university students, particularly those pursuing rigorous academic disciplines like medicine, are especially reliant on the internet for educational purposes, social networking, entertainment, and academic research [1]. While the internet serves as a powerful educational tool, its excessive and

uncontrolled use may lead to behavioral issues, prominently including internet addiction (IA). Internet addiction is broadly defined as the inability to control one's internet use, resulting in marked distress and functional impairment [2]. This behavioral pattern is closely aligned with impulse control disorders and can interfere with academic, personal, and social life [3].

Dr. Kimberly Young, a pioneer in this field, developed the Young's Internet Addiction Test (IAT) to systematically evaluate and quantify the severity of addictive internet behavior [4]. Medical students, due to the academic demands of their

coursework and the stressors inherent to medical training, are highly susceptible to internet addiction. The medical curriculum often requires long hours of study, case discussions, and continued exposure to screens, leading many students to shift seamlessly from academic internet use to recreational browsing, gaming, and social media scrolling [5]. Prolonged internet use for non-academic purposes may disturb sleep cycles, reduce academic productivity, and increase levels of anxiety and depression [6].

In India, the rise in internet penetration has been remarkable, with over 900 million users as of 2024, making it the second-largest internet-using population in the world [7]. A significant portion of this user base comprises young adults and college students, making the issue of internet addiction particularly pertinent in the Indian context. Various studies across Indian medical colleges have found that the prevalence of internet addiction ranges from 25% to over 50% depending on the location, assessment tool used, and the demographics of the population studied [8].

A study conducted by Sharma et al. (2020) in northern India revealed that 45% of medical students showed signs of mild to moderate internet addiction, with males and hostel dwellers being more affected [9]. Similar findings were echoed by Goel et al. (2013), who observed a significant association between internet addiction and poor academic performance, increased stress levels, and social withdrawal among students [10].

Psychologically, internet addiction has been linked to a wide spectrum of behavioral and emotional disturbances. It is often comorbid with anxiety disorders, depressive symptoms, sleep disturbances, and even symptoms of attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) [11]. Medical students affected by IA may suffer from poor concentration, low academic achievement, and a diminished sense of well-being, which can further compound the challenges of an already demanding educational path [12].

Additionally, the COVID-19 pandemic exacerbated dependence on digital devices and online platforms for education, social interaction, and leisure, significantly increasing screen time across all demographics [13]. The post-pandemic academic landscape remains digitally inclined, maintaining many of the behaviors and dependencies established during lockdown periods.

Despite the growing concern, there remains a paucity of region-specific data on internet addiction in Rajasthan, particularly among medical students. Most existing studies are concentrated in metropolitan regions, leaving a research gap in smaller cities like Udaipur. This gap is important to

address, given the cultural and infrastructural differences that may influence internet use behaviors in semi-urban educational settings.

Given the potential consequences of internet addiction on academic performance, mental health, and social functioning, there is a pressing need to assess its prevalence, identify high-risk groups, and promote preventive strategies. The present study seeks to evaluate the magnitude of internet addiction among medical students in Udaipur using the standardized Young's Internet Addiction Test, and to explore its associations with socio-demographic and behavioral factors.

Understanding the pattern and severity of internet addiction in this population will not only contribute to the academic literature but also provide a foundation for targeted interventions, such as digital wellness programs, counseling services, and awareness campaigns. These findings may help medical educators and administrators to foster a healthier and more balanced use of technology among students—ultimately improving their academic performance and mental health.

Methods and Materials

Study Design and Setting: This study was a cross-sectional, descriptive, questionnaire-based study conducted in three recognized medical colleges in Udaipur, Rajasthan, India. These institutions were selected due to their sizeable undergraduate MBBS student population and accessibility for data collection.

Study Period: This study was conducted for 3 months, October to December 2024.

Study Population: The study population comprised MBBS students from first to final year. Students of both genders and various residential backgrounds (hostel or home) were included. The internet use behavior of this population made them appropriate subjects for studying internet addiction.

Inclusion Criteria

- MBBS students aged 18 to 25 years.
- Students who were currently using the internet daily for academic or non-academic purposes.
- Those who provided informed written consent.

Exclusion Criteria

- Students with a known psychiatric illness or those on psychotropic medication.
- Incompletely filled questionnaires.
- Students who declined consent.

Sample Size Calculation: Assuming an expected prevalence of internet addiction to be 50% (maximum variability), with 5% absolute precision and 95% confidence level, the sample size was calculated using the formula:

$$n = Z^2 \times P \times (1-P) / d^2$$

Where,

$Z = 1.96$ for 95% CI,

$p = 0.5$,

$d = 0.05$

$$n = (1.96)^2 \times 0.05 \times 0.05 / (0.05)^2 = 384$$

After adding 5% for non-response, the final sample size was 403 students.

Sampling Technique: A stratified random sampling technique was employed. The total sample of 400 students was proportionally allocated across the four academic years (First Year, Second Year, Third Year, and Final Year). Within each stratum (year), simple random sampling was done to select participants.

Study Tool: A pre-tested, structured, self-administered questionnaire was used, consisting of two parts:

Section A: Socio-demographic and Behavioral Details

It included information such as age, gender, year of study, residence, average daily internet use, purpose of use of internet.

Section B: Young's Internet Addiction Test (IAT)

- Developed by Kimberly Young [1], the 20-item IAT is a validated tool for assessing internet addiction.
- Each item is scored on a 5-point Likert scale from 0 (Not at all) to 5 (Always).

Total scores range from 0 to 100, categorized as:

- 0–30: Normal use
- 31–49: Mild addiction

- 50–79: Moderate addiction
- 80–100: Severe addiction

Data Collection Procedure: Data were collected in classroom settings after obtaining prior permission from college authorities and informed consent from the students. The objective of the study was explained to the participants, and they were assured of anonymity and confidentiality. Students completed the questionnaire in approximately 15–20 minutes without discussion.

Ethical Considerations:

Participation was voluntary, and written informed consent was obtained from each participant. The study ensured strict confidentiality, and no personal identifiers were recorded.

Data Analysis: Data were entered in Microsoft Excel and analyzed using IBM SPSS version 25.0, with descriptive statistics including mean, standard deviation, frequency, and percentage used to summarize participant characteristics and Internet Addiction Test (IAT) scores, while inferential statistics such as the Chi-square test were applied to examine associations between categorical variables like gender, residence, and internet usage patterns with levels of internet addiction, considering a p-value of less than 0.05 as statistically significant.

Results

Out of 403 medical students approached, 392 responded completely, giving a response rate of 98%. The mean age of participants was 20.8 ± 1.5 years. Among the participants, 54.3% ($n = 213$) were female and 45.7% ($n = 179$) were male. 58.2% ($n = 228$) were hostel residents, while 41.8% ($n = 164$) lived at home. The majority of students, 37.5% ($n = 147$), belonged to the second year of MBBS. (Table 1)

Table 1: Sociodemographic Characteristics of Participants (n = 392)

Variable		Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age Group (in years)	18–19	86	21.9
	20–21	218	55.6
	22–24	88	22.4
Gender	Male	179	45.7
	Female	213	54.3
Year of Study	First Year	89	22.7
	Second Year	147	37.5
	Third Year	97	24.7
	Final Year	59	15.1
Residence	Hostel	228	58.2
	Home	164	41.8

Internet Usage Behavior: Most students, 61.7% ($n = 242$), reported using the internet for more than 4 hours per day, while only 10.5% ($n = 41$) used it for less than 2 hours. Academic use was reported as the primary purpose by 44.4% ($n = 174$), whereas non-academic use (social media, entertainment, gaming) was reported by 55.6% ($n = 218$). (Table 2)

Table 2: Internet Usage Pattern of Participants

Internet Use Variables		Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Average Internet Use (Daily)	<2 hours	41	10.5
	2–4 hours	109	27.8
	>4 hours	242	61.7
Primary Purpose of Use	Academic	174	44.4
	Non-academic	218	55.6

Internet Addiction Scores: Based on the Young's Internet Addiction Test (IAT), the distribution of internet addiction among the 392 medical students revealed that 92 students (23.5%) were classified as normal internet users with scores ranging from 0 to

30, while 173 students (44.1%) exhibited mild addiction (scores 31–49), 111 students (28.3%) had moderate addiction (scores 50–79), and 16 students (4.1%) were found to have severe internet addiction with scores between 80 and 100.(Table 3)

Table 3: Distribution of Internet Addiction Levels (n = 392)

IAT Score Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
0–30 (Normal)	92	23.5
31–49 (Mild)	173	44.1
50–79 (Moderate)	111	28.3
80–100 (Severe)	16	4.1

Association between Demographics and Internet Addiction: Male students had a significantly higher prevalence of moderate to severe internet addiction compared to female students ($p = 0.03$), and students residing in hostels showed greater levels of addiction than those living at home ($p = 0.01$). A strong association was observed between

daily internet use of more than 4 hours and moderate to severe addiction ($p < 0.001$), indicating that increased screen time is a key predictor of higher addiction levels. However, no statistically significant difference in addiction levels was found across different years of study. (Table 4)

Table 4: Association of Internet Addiction with Selected Variables

Variable		Normal (%)	Mild (%)	Moderate/Severe (%)	p-value
Gender	Male	17.9	41.3	40.8	0.03*
	Female	28.6	46.5	24.9	
Residence	Hostel	18.4	43.4	38.2	0.01*
	Home	30.5	45.1	24.4	
Daily Use	<2 hours	51.2	36.6	12.2	<0.001**
	2–4 hours	31.2	44.9	23.9	
	>4 hours	14.5	46.3	39.2	

*Significant at $p < 0.05$; **Highly significant at $p < 0.001$

Key observations from the study revealed that nearly one in three students (32.4%) exhibited moderate to severe internet addiction, highlighting a substantial concern among medical undergraduates. Students who primarily used the internet for non-academic purposes had significantly higher IAT scores compared to those using it for academic activities. Additionally, female students were predominantly found in the normal or mild addiction categories, whereas male students had a higher representation in the moderate to severe addiction categories, indicating a gender-based variation in internet usage patterns and addiction severity.

Discussion

This study aimed to assess the prevalence and pattern of internet addiction among medical students in Udaipur using the Young's Internet

Addiction Test (IAT). The findings revealed that a significant proportion of students—32.4%—were found to have moderate to severe levels of internet addiction. This aligns closely with earlier studies conducted across India and globally, indicating that internet addiction is an emerging public health concern in the academic environment [1,2]. The mean age of participants was approximately 21 years, and the addiction pattern was most prominent among students aged 20–22, which is consistent with the findings of Sharma et al., who reported a higher prevalence of internet addiction in early adulthood among professional course students [9]. The high prevalence of mild (44.1%) and moderate (28.3%) internet addiction observed in our study parallels findings from Goel et al., who reported a 26.3% prevalence of moderate addiction in Indian adolescents [10]. Gender differences in internet addiction were evident, with male students

exhibiting significantly higher levels of moderate to severe addiction compared to females. This trend is supported by several previous studies, which suggest that males are more prone to excessive internet use, especially for gaming, entertainment, and social media purposes [11,14]. Possible explanations include behavioral tendencies toward risk-taking and impulsivity, as well as gender-specific preferences for online content.

Hostel residence was another significant predictor, with hostellers showing higher rates of internet addiction than their counterparts living at home. This supports the findings by Dixit et al. and Alavi et al., who found that greater independence and fewer parental restrictions in hostel environments contribute to prolonged and unsupervised internet use [8,5].

One of the strongest associations observed was between daily internet usage and addiction severity. Students using the internet for more than four hours per day had a significantly higher likelihood of moderate to severe addiction. This relationship has been consistently reported in the literature, highlighting the role of screen time in determining the risk of internet addiction [15,13].

Although internet use for academic purposes was common, non-academic use such as social media browsing, video streaming, and online gaming predominated among those with higher IAT scores. This is in agreement with research from Lam and Peng, which found that excessive use of the internet for non-educational purposes was strongly linked to emotional and behavioral disturbances [6].

The relatively small proportion (4.1%) of students with severe internet addiction in this study may reflect the limited time medical students have outside academic responsibilities. However, even moderate levels of addiction can have consequences on sleep quality, academic performance, and mental well-being, as suggested by Ko et al. and Kandell [3,12].

Interestingly, no statistically significant association was found between the year of study and internet addiction. This finding contrasts with studies such as those by Kuss and Griffiths, which observed increasing addiction levels among higher-year students due to greater academic pressure and screen dependency [11]. The lack of such a trend in this study may be due to uniform digital engagement across all years during and after the COVID-19 pandemic, which significantly increased reliance on online learning across all academic levels [16].

Overall, these findings highlight the pressing need for awareness programs, digital wellness initiatives, and counseling services tailored to medical

students. Early identification and intervention can help mitigate the adverse impacts of internet addiction on students' physical, mental, and academic health.

Conclusion

This study highlights a significant prevalence of internet addiction among medical students in Udaipur, with nearly one-third exhibiting moderate to severe addiction. Key contributing factors included male gender, hostel residence, excessive daily usage, and non-academic internet use. These findings underline the urgent need for awareness programs on digital wellness, promotion of balanced screen time, and incorporation of mental health support in medical institutions. Colleges should consider structured interventions such as workshops, counseling services, and digital detox campaigns to address and prevent excessive internet use. However, the study has certain limitations, including its cross-sectional nature which precludes causal inference, reliance on self-reported data that may be subject to reporting bias, and restriction to only medical students in Udaipur, which limits generalizability. Future multicentric and longitudinal studies are recommended to explore the long-term impact of internet addiction on academic performance, mental health, and professional development.

References

1. Anderson KJ. Internet use among college students: An exploratory study. *J Am Coll Health*. 2001; 50(1):21–6.
2. Block JJ. Issues for DSM-V: Internet addiction. *Am J Psychiatry*. 2008; 165(3):306–7.
3. Ko CH, Yen JY, Chen CC, Chen SH, Yen CF. Predictive values of psychiatric symptoms for Internet addiction in adolescents: A 2-year prospective study. *Arch Pediatr Adolesc Med*. 2009; 163(10):937–43.
4. Young KS. Internet addiction: The emergence of a new clinical disorder. *CyberPsychol Behav*. 1998; 1(3):237–44.
5. Alavi SS, Maracy MR, Jannatifard F, Eslami M. The effect of psychiatric symptoms on the Internet addiction disorder in Isfahan's University students. *J Res Med Sci*. 2011; 16(6):793–800.
6. Lam LT, Peng ZW. Effect of pathological use of the Internet on adolescent mental health: A prospective study. *Arch Pediatr Adolesc Med*. 2010; 164(10):901–6.
7. Internet and Mobile Association of India (IAMAI). Internet in India 2024 report. [Available online].
8. Dixit S, Shukla H, Bhagwat AK, Bindal A, Goyal A, Zaidi AK. A study to evaluate internet addiction disorder among students of a

- medical college and associated hospital of Central India. *Natl J Community Med.* 2010; 1(2):279–85.
9. Sharma A, Sahu R, Kasar PK, Sharma R. Internet addiction among professional courses students: A study from central India. *Int J Med Sci Public Health.* 2014; 3(9):1069–73.
 10. Goel D, Subramanyam A, Kamath R. A study on the prevalence of internet addiction and its association with psychopathology in Indian adolescents. *Indian J Psychiatry.* 2013; 55(2):140–3.
 11. Kuss DJ, Griffiths MD. Internet addiction in students: Prevalence and risk factors. *Comput Human Behav.* 2011; 29(3):959–66.
 12. Kandell JJ. Internet addiction on campus: The vulnerability of college students. *CyberPsychol Behav.* 1998; 1(1):11–7.
 13. Gupta R, Dhamija G, Patil M. COVID-19 and internet usage: A study on digital behavior of students during lockdown. *Int J Contemp Med Res.* 2021; 8(1):A1–4.
 14. Ching SM, Awang H, Ramachandran V, Sazlly Lim SM, Mohd Sazlly Lim S, Wan Sulaiman WA, et al. Prevalence and factors associated with internet addiction among medical students in Malaysia. *Med J Malaysia.* 2017; 72(1):7–11.
 15. Nalwa K, Anand AP. Internet addiction in students: A cause of concern. *Cyberpsychol Behav.* 2003; 6(6):653–6.
 16. Singh S, Roy D, Sinha K, Parveen S, Sharma G, Joshi G. Impact of COVID-19 and lockdown on mental health of children and adolescents: A narrative review with recommendations. *Psychiatry Res.* 2020; 293:113429.